

Economic disparities and clientelism in Romania. A subnational analysis

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Abstract

This paper analyses the relationship between demand-driven clientelism, economic disparities, and public expenditures at the county level in Romania. Using several economic and social indicators we realize an in-depth analysis of economic development disparities in Romania concerning the clientelistic incidence of the Romanian parties. The latter was based on an extensive original survey developed in the first quarter of 2021 regarding clientelism perception among 42 counties of Romania for both national (parliamentary) and local elections, addressing both positive and negative clientelism approaches. Thus, we tested if, in Romania, greater economic constraints increase the individuals' propensity to engage in a clientelistic relationship with political parties or candidates and the correlation of local public expenditures (social protection and personnel local expenditures) with the incidence of clientelism.

Keywords

clientelism; subnational disparities; economic welfare; public expenditures; voting

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Introduction

During the last decades, the economic disparities among counties increased in Romania, often within the same county (e.g., the county-capital relatively to other cities or urban areas compared with rural areas). In general, the main economic causes of this phenomena are deeply embedded in the local structural conditions. Here we can mention the basic economic activities specialization (e.g. agriculture, services, manufacturing), lack of entrepreneurial abilities at the local level (e.g. number of active private companies at 1000 persons or exporting companies), human capital quality (e.g. low-skilled or high-skilled individuals) and net migration, physical capital endowments (e.g. transport infrastructure, industrial parks), institutional (e.g. corruption) or the local public administration capacity to implement high-quality public policies to achieve economic development (e.g. FDI inflows, local EU funds, support for SMEs creation) (Volintiru et al., 2018; Romanian Government, 2018; Farole et al., 2018).

These factors among others inhibit the economic growth to spread smoothly within Romanian counties and regions. Even if the national average of Gross Domestic Product converged with the EU average at PPP, from this process some regions benefit, while other regions lag with impact on social outcomes (health, education, access to information, voice), but also on poverty (European Commission, 2017)³.

However, to attenuate the impact of the uneven economic development among counties, the central government and the local public administration (county councils, city-halls) created different types of interventions and public policies support. For example, starting with 2007 the Romanian Government implemented several state aid schemes for regional development and jobs creation to support private investments⁴, while through social assistance schemes significant amounts of money were transferred to vulnerable citizens, especially in the poorer regions (North-East and South regions), creating thus incentives for different types of clientelism⁵. Moreover, we should also mention the dominance of public sector employment (public administration, defense, education, health, social security) in some counties where the private sector is less developed and the public sector has an important role to play in offering local individuals more opportunities on the labor market.

This article contributes at a better understanding of the relationship between several types of clientelism at the local (county) level in Romania via different types of local public expenditures and assesses how the local public expenditures are correlated and could represent a potential monetary vehicle between “patrons” and “clients”. The empirical analysis is based on two main data sources: (i) public data regarding the expenditures from Romanian local public administrations aggregated at the county level by different types of expenditures and (ii) an extensive survey regarding the incidence of clientelism at the local level in the last election process (parliamentary and local elections from 2020).

The paper is organized as follows. In the first part of the article, we analyzed the literature regarding clientelism and economic development emphasizing the characteristics of demand-driven clientelism and the influence of economic conditions. In the second part, we presented the

³ In Romania, for example, the Bucharest-Ilfov region surpasses Madrid, Berlin, or Budapest, in terms of GDP per capita, but that same country also has 5 regions that rank among the poorest in all of the EU (Farole and Goga, 2017).

⁴ The Romanian government implemented several state aid schemes concentrated on helping private companies from underdeveloped regions and jobs creation from 2010 to 2019 via direct grants or interest subsidies: regional development (2,11 billion EUR), sectoral development (169 million EUR), SMEs including risk capital (26 million EUR) (Data: https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/comp/redisstat/databrowser/view/AID_SCB_OBJ/default/table).

⁵ Between 2010-2020 the local public budgets social expenditures represented 940 million EUR (4,2 billion RON).

methodology and the data sources. The third part of the paper covers an in-depth analysis of economic development disparities in Romania and the correlation with clientelism at the county level based on the perception of citizens' clientelistic approaches of the Romanian parties, several economic indicators, and public expenditures. Finally, the fourth part presents the main conclusions and further research directions that can be followed.

Clientelism, poverty and public expenditures

Clientelism can be seen as a process of extracting and accumulating public resources through which political “patrons” informal distribute them towards beneficiaries in the exchange of the vote or political support (Cornelius, 1977). Because political owners control public resources in a discretionary manner, an asymmetric power relationship between “patrons” and “clients” is consolidated, altering the democratic relationship between the voter and the elected representative.

Moreover, the clientelistic exchanges strengthen the domination and control of political “patrons” over voters through “coercive dependence” (Fattouh 1986, p.61). This type of relationship has been predominantly analyzed in under-developed economic environments, where the power gap between politicians and voters is large in terms of wealth. Thus, an important determinant of clientelism is poverty, with poor voters having a high economic pressure on them to meet the short term needs and being much more likely to respond to the use of clientelistic benefits in exchange for votes (Bobonis et al., 2017; Frey, 2019; Stokes et al., 2013; Stokes, 2021).

Clientelism can also inhibit a country's or region's economic progress. The basic premise of this theory is that government initiatives at both the national and local levels are unsuccessful in addressing the need for vulnerable persons to escape their socio-economic marginalization. This is sometimes intended to make voters more dependent on politicians and thus make it easier for them to buy political support by offering jobs or other forms of monetary or in-kind benefits in return.

For Romania, but also in the case of other post-communist countries, the transition to capitalism provided ample space for the development of clientele networks, especially amid weak institutions, weak formal accountability mechanisms, but also because of strengthened informal exchange relations (Volintiru, 2016). Thus, we can speak of situations in which private contractors may be dependent on public procurement from the state, not only as an act of corruption by which public contracts are discretionarily offered to private sector companies close to the ruling parties, but also as part of a clientelistic system fed with financial resources such as private donations (see Gherghina and Volintiru, 2017).

Moreover, the same clientelistic system includes companies that can play an important role in the electoral mobilization of employees (Mareş et al., 2018), the management of a private company forcing own employees to vote (or not to vote) for a particular candidate or party. Mareş et al. (2018) show that employee intimidation plays an important role in clientelistic strategies in Romania and Bulgaria, especially in localities where the number of companies is small and citizens have fewer employment opportunities.

The literature on the relationship between deprived citizens and political patrons is heavily concentrated on the clientelistic systems of Latin America. It is predominantly in urban slums and poor areas where informal distributional patterns prevail in the quasi-absence of formal social systems. This string of the literature showcases through qualitative studies the extent to which clientelism is demand-driven, as political machines respond to citizens needs and want by “request fulfilling” (Auyero, 1999; Auyero, 2000; Nichter and Peress, 2017). In the context of poor service provided by the state and consolidated informal networks at the local level, it is precisely the clientelistic exchanges

that enhance the credibility of political candidates (Huisman, 2020; Keefer and Vlaicu, 2008; Manzetti and Wilson, 2007; Morgan and Kelly, 2017; Stokes et al., 2013)

The most common objects of clientelistic exchanges in the context of underdevelopment and poverty are social assistance benefits. These can take the form of direct transfers or national subsidy programs for vulnerable groups (e.g. unemployed, poor families, people with disabilities). One of the most commonly used clientelistic benefits distributed is conditional cash transfer (Stokes et al., 2013). According to the World Health Organization (2008), conditional cash transfer programs provide money to households on the condition that they meet certain predefined requirements (e.g. regular school attendance, regular visits to a medical center, and vaccination). While international organizations support such programs and consider them an effective way to reduce poverty, political “patrons” sometimes support these programs to select the beneficiaries preferentially in exchange for votes.⁶

Social assistance mechanisms are essential tools to support the economically vulnerable population, especially in countries with high disparities between individual incomes and regions/counties⁷. However, they can easily become discretionary instruments in the hands of public authorities whose activity is not subject to public monitoring or control by competent bodies. Thus, those mechanisms dedicated to supporting the poor population (economically vulnerable) become instruments through which voters end up in a clientelistic situation in the context of underdevelopment and poverty.

A structural aspect in the relationship between economic policies and clientelism is highlighted by Robinson and Verdier (2013), who argue that in democracies the political power is more evenly distributed than revenue (or assets) and therefore there is pressure to redistribute revenue, including to “clients”. They also show that inefficient redistribution and clientelism become attractive as a political strategy especially in areas where there is high inequality and low labor productivity, on the one hand, but also when in politics the pecuniary interests dominate ideology, on the other hand. This perspective sees clientelism as a “poverty trap”, where poor “government policy arises as a way of making voters more dependent on politicians, and hence making it easier to buy their political support with job offers” (Robinson and Verdier, 2013: 262). An important example of this situation that appears in scientific literature is in Southern Italy. Although it has received substantial transfers from the government, the redistribution of resources has not been accompanied over time by economic development (Chubb, 1981). Additionally, Alesina et al. (1999) affirm that around 50% of those employed in the public sector in Southern Italy were employed as a result of a clientelistic relationship.

However, other dimensions could be highlighted in terms of the patron-client relationship. First of all, through these informal clientelistic relations, a mechanism for transmitting the needs of the disadvantaged population to decision-makers is strengthened, which in the absence of the clientelistic system could not exist (Brun and Diamond, 2014). Poor communities are not only socially

⁶ Poverty is usually defined as the material condition of individuals in terms of income (or consumption) over a period of time. It can be measured both as absolute poverty (i.e. monetary units per day / month / year) and in relative terms (relative to other individuals in society). The most relevant indicator is relative poverty, because it also takes into account the dynamics of society as a whole and captures how individuals manage to evolve at a similar or lower rate to the society to which they belong. This is measured in relation to a certain statistical threshold, usually set at 60% of the median income of the population (see, for example, the methodology of Eurostat or the World Bank).

⁷ Inequality of income distribution S80/S20 income quintile share ratio - EU-SILC and ECHP surveys [ilc_pns4] – 7,21 for Romania in 2020 and an average of 7,54 from 2007 to 2020.

marginalized, but they are also politically marginalized, with policymakers often paying less attention to them. These vulnerable groups are thus integrated through electoral clientele systems intended at the mass mobilization of particular categories of voters on election day who are motivated by the desire to acquire goods, products, jobs, and services in exchange for voting. As a result, despite the suboptimal public goods and services to which they are formally entitled as citizens of a state, voters get a little more in the clientelistic system than they do in a precarious administrative system that fails to integrate and satisfy their demands in an institutional (formal) manner.

Secondly, the clientelistic system inevitably raises the status of its beneficiaries. Beyond buying votes on election day, clientelism involves a series of *one-off* transactions (e.g., approval of applications and permits, notices) and continuously (e.g., employment in the public system, access to social assistance services, preferential access to public goods) which provides material security to the beneficiaries. Thus, through successive iterations, customers can get out of “captive clientele” status and increase their well-being. Clients of formal redistributive systems (beneficiaries of legal welfare programs) or informal ones can eventually disconnect from the dependence of political patrons facilitated by poverty: “permanent poverty reductions can break the voter's dependence on clientelism” (Frey, 2019: 2).

An important body of literature correlates clientelism with state weakness: low ability to control violence, rule of law, regulatory capacity, tax evasion, and low levels of public good provision (Stokes et al. 2013; Diaz-Cayeros et al., 2016; Fergusson et al., 2015; Fergusson et al., 2020). Fergusson et al., (2015) consider that clientelistic parties have incentives to undermine state capacity to supply public goods to maintain their electoral comparative advantage, especially when faced with political rivalry.

Moreover, Fergusson et al. (2020) show that there is a significant correlation between state weakness, measured by tax evasion, and the propensity to engage in clientelistic relationships in Columbia. The authors note that clients of political patrons are more likely to evade taxes, while there is “no ethical inhibition in admitting to engaging in either tax evasion or clientelism” (Fergusson et al., 2020: 3) in countries with weak states and with lower levels of public good provision. Tribin (2020) also examines the distribution of public resources in the case of incumbents seeking re-election using public expenditures in Colombia. The author affirms that cash transfers are a faster and easier technique of addressing voters because they provide immediate gratification. As a result, they're an excellent tool for persuading municipalities with skeptic voters. Moreover, an incumbent with public goods can make long-term and slow-moving investments that are useful to reward partisans in both swing and core municipalities”, the author claims.

On the same topic, Song (2020) investigates whether public campaign financing is useful in inspiring people to run for office and helping them in winning in the case of South Korea. His findings reveal that, regardless of campaign expense reimbursement, “public financing had no overall effect on candidate reemergence and success” in a subsequent election.

Explaining the behavior of government relating to public expenditures in Sub-Saharan African countries but also some Western democracies like Italy and France, Bohn (2007) suggests that, amid polarization and potentially political instability (i.e. high government's probability of losing power), the government has to resolve a trade-off between efficient public investment (i.e. capital expenditures in education, infrastructure or health) and redistribution. He affirms that in order to maintain power, the government “totally refrains from spending on public investment if there is heavy discounting produced by political instability” (Bohn, 2007, p. 8), resulting in underinvestment.

Another aspect discussed in the literature is the connection between clientelism – especially in the form of vote-buying, corruption, and voting turnout. Analyzing the relationship between corruption and political participation in Italian municipalities, Giommoni, citing Putnam (1993), affirms that turnout is a measure of civic engagement and “places with more social capital face less vote buying and clientelism, and political participation is more likely to be motivated by civic spirit. Thus, corruption exposure is more effective where citizens vote according to moral concerns rather than for material interests” (Giommoni, 2021: 18).

Our paper highlights the demand-driven clientelism based on the individuals’ economic constraints (i.e. individual willingness to be involved in clientelistic relation) and also the incidence of local clientelism concerning two types of public expenditures (i.e. social assistance, and personnel), in line with the literature findings on the use of welfare and public employment as vehicles of the client-patron transactions. In our study, the main research hypotheses are related to economic disparities (constraints), public expenditures, and clientelism incidence at the local (i.e. county) level in Romania. Thus, we have two main hypotheses:

H1. Greater economic constraints (i.e. high poverty rate, high unemployment rate, low GDP per capita) increase the individuals’ propensity to engage in a clientelistic relationship with political parties or persons;

H2. Higher public expenditures (social protection and personnel local expenditures) are directly correlated with a high incidence of clientelism at the local level.

Methodology and data sources

To analyze the characteristics of clientelism and its relationship with economic development in Romania we use a combination of quantitative and qualitative analysis. First, we conducted an original systematic comparative survey at the subnational level in Romania that accounts for the prevalence of clientelism in its different forms (e.g. vote-buying, access to social benefits, access to public goods and services, public jobs). The survey was realized after the 2020 elections, including questions for both local and parliamentary elections.

We applied an extensive survey on more than 4000 individuals older than 18 years from both urban and rural areas (N=4316, of which = 202 from capital city Bucharest, 113 from Cluj, 101 from Dolj, and 100 from the rest of 38 counties). Most respondents are from three main age groups: 26-35 years, 46-45 years, and 56-65 years. Almost three quarters of the respondents have a net income lower than 4000 lei, representing a monthly net income of around 813 EUR at an average exchange rate in 2021 of 1 EUR = 4,92 Lei.

We linked the results obtained from the survey to the local economic environment (i.e. using indicators such as GDP per capita and the unemployment rate) for all 42 Romanian counties. Additionally, we collected the local public expenditures realized from 2010 to 2020 by different functions, emphasizing the importance of social protection and personnel expenditures (as share in total public local expenditures).

Subsequently, the local public expenditures were divided into two main types: (i) *investment expenditures* (capital spending and EU funds spending from local budgets) and (ii) *passive expenditures* (social protection and personnel expenditures) to highlight the local authorities’ inclination towards short-term political benefits (i.e. public jobs offering in the public sector and social benefits for citizens) or long-term benefits via investment spending at the local level in various sectors (health, education or infrastructure) in line with Bohn (2007) arguments.

As previously mentioned, our main research hypotheses are related to economic disparities (constraints), public expenditures, and clientelism incidence at the local (i.e. county) level in Romania. Economic indicators are obtained from the Romanian National Institute of Statistics (Tempo online database), while local public expenditures by function at the county level were collected from the Ministry of Development, Public Works, and Administration⁸.

At the same time, to emphasize the role of clientelism at the local level we split the survey answers and analysis between positive and negative clientelistic approaches of the Romanian parties. The positive and negative clientelism approaches are covered by two types of questions regarding the respondent's perception of the following items:

Q1. Positive clientelism: During the 2020 elections, was any of your acquaintances offered one of the following by a candidate or political party? (Multiple answers, please check all that apply): (1) Bag of products or food; (2) Possibility of a job after elections; (3) Money; (4) Access to social assistance benefits.

Q2. Negative clientelism: During the 2020 election, was any of your acquaintances threatened by a candidate or political party with one of the following? (Multiple answers, please check all that apply): (1) Loss of access to social assistance benefits; (2) Loss of job after elections; (3) Loss of access to certain public goods; (4) Loss of access to free public services.

Additionally, to emphasize the demand-driven clientelism and citizens expectations, we included in the survey the following question for both parliamentary and local election rounds:

Q3. Some citizens approach candidates and ask them for access to services or to offer them something in exchange for voting in elections. Do you know people who had such an approach in the 2020 elections?

Furthermore, we realized a statistical analysis of the respondents' answers and also a different statistical correlation between the incidence of clientelism (overall, but also positive and negative clientelism types) among Romanian counties and socio-economic indicators mentioned above (GDP per capita and unemployment rate)⁹.

The level of (under)development in Romania - regional disparities and exposure to clientelism
In Romania, despite the economic growth recorded since joining the European Union (according to Eurostat, the Gross Domestic Product per capita at purchasing power parity has reached in 2020 a level of 72% of the EU27 average¹⁰), the distribution of this growth from a geographical point of view was quite uneven. The GDP per capita in some counties and regions has increased more than in others, depending on how each county has managed to use its competitive advantages, to increase the number of employees, to attract as high a flow of foreign direct investment as possible, to increase their contribution to exports, etc. These have gradually become more concentrated in the capital Bucharest and some counties, with direct repercussions on living standards¹¹.

Romania has seen a sharp increase in regional disparities, especially after 1989, during the post-communist transition. If in the early 1990s, four out of eight regions had a GDP per capita higher than the national average, in 2018 this was only valid for two of them (FES, 2020). The same FES report

⁸ http://www.dpfbf.mdrap.ro/sit_ven_si_chelt_uat.html.

⁹ Additional results are available upon request from the authors.

¹⁰ Eurostat, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tec00114/default/table?lang=en> (PRC PPP IND).

¹¹ The report of the National Plan for the euro currency adoption, Government of Romania, December 2018.

states that “if in 1993 GDP per capita did not fall in any of the regions below 80% of the national average, in 2018 the Northeast Region had only 63% of the national average of GDP per capita” (FES, 2020: 5).

Using different socio-economic indicators, Lupu (2018) shows that in Romania there are several important disparities. The paper differentiates between several existing clusters¹² in Romania and shows that Bucharest, Ilfov, Sibiu, Brașov, and Constanța are counties where poverty is less present, mainly due to the diversified economic structure, attracted foreign investments and access to public services, education, and good quality sanitary infrastructure. Several counties have been severely affected by socio-economic changes since the mid-1990s and after 2000, where living standards are low, infrastructure is underdeveloped, housing is precarious, there is a large share of the rural population and income inequality is very high. In these areas, the local budgets register very low revenues, depopulation, and the fact that land use and development allocations are generally low. Here are mentioned especially counties from North-East region, such as Botoșani, Neamț, Suceava, Vaslui, Buzău, but also from other counties in the South of the country: Teleorman, Vrancea, Călărași, Dâmbovița, Giurgiu, Ialomița, Mehedinți, and Olt.

Figure 1. Poverty risk rates at the regional and county level

Source: World Bank (2016)

The World Bank (2016) analyzed poverty in Romania at the level of regions and counties, dividing the 42 counties into 8 intervals according to the determined risk of poverty. Even if the methodology is different, the results are relatively similar to those obtained by Lupu (2018). The report identifies the poorest counties, in which over 28% of the population is below the poverty line: Botoșani, Vaslui, Suceava, Iași, Neamț, Vrancea, Buzău, Galați, Giurgiu, Călărași, Teleorman, Olt, Mehedinți,

¹² In the case of the cluster analysis, several categories of socio-economic indicators were selected at county level: income level (average gross monthly salary), access to services and living conditions (number of people in the household, share of housing without network access to water supply, sewerage, electricity or central heating, the share of households without a kitchen or bathroom in the house, the share of the rural population, the number of doctors per 1000 inhabitants and the number of medical units); the level of education (the share of the school-age population that is not included in the education system and the share of higher education graduates); employment level (total employment rate and employment rates in agriculture and services); degree of economic development (regional GDP per capita, FDI), and demographic characteristics (rate of demographic dependence).

Caraș-Severin, Săl and Satu Mare (see Figure 1). The highest incidence of poverty is found in Botoșani, Vrancea, and Vaslui counties.

The results obtained by Lupu (2018) and World Bank (2016) are strengthened also by the statistical indicators from Romanian National Institute for Statistics regarding the GDP per capita (Figure 2), especially by the standard deviation evolution during 2010 and 2020. In this period the standard deviation of GDP per capita among all Romanian counties increased from 8,2 to 18,6 thousand RON amid rapid increases registered in the richer counties.

Figure 2. Median, average, and standard deviation of GDP per capita (2010-2020)

Source: Authors' calculation, based on National Institute of Statistics data

Increasing disparities among counties, on one hand, and also between urban and rural regions, on the other hand, have exposed a large number of persons to poverty and precarious standards of living. This context created the soil for clientelistic approaches as individuals seek to cover immediate basic needs while politicians respond consequently offering food, social assistance benefits, or jobs opportunity in the public sector.

The next section presents the economic constraints at the local level (i.e. GDP per capita and unemployment rate at county level) in correlation with individual willingness to participate in clientelistic relationships and incidence of different forms of clientelism.

Clientelism incidence and economic indicators

Based on the survey implemented in January-March 2021 we correlated the answers to the questions described above, in the Methodology section, and several economic indicators.

First, Figure 3 shows the incidence of positive and negative types of clientelism among Romanian respondents where we emphasized the dominance of positive clientelism. By type, offering food, job opportunities and social benefits are the most used forms of positive clientelistic instruments

used at the local level. It should also be noted that positive clientelism is used more intensely for the local elections than for the national parliamentary elections (see also Table 1).

Figure 3. Incidence of Positive (top) and Negative (bottom) types of clientelism

Source: authors' calculations.

Table 1. Clientelism incidence at the local and the national parliamentary elections

County	Local elections 2020			National elections 2020		
	Positive	Negative	Difference	Positive	Negative	Difference
Alba	7,0%	4,8%	2,3%	12,0%	9,0%	3,0%
Arad	9,0%	7,3%	1,8%	18,8%	11,5%	7,3%
Argeş	13,0%	10,3%	2,8%	14,3%	8,3%	6,0%
Bacău	16,0%	13,3%	2,8%	18,3%	11,5%	6,8%
Bihor	6,3%	7,5%	-1,3%	12,5%	10,0%	2,5%
Bistriţa Năsăud	11,0%	7,0%	4,0%	14,3%	11,3%	3,0%
Botoşani	12,0%	8,5%	3,5%	23,0%	12,5%	10,5%
Braşov	6,5%	3,8%	2,8%	15,5%	9,3%	6,3%
Brăila	9,0%	6,0%	3,0%	9,5%	6,8%	2,8%
Bucureşti	8,8%	4,2%	4,6%	13,9%	6,6%	7,3%
Buzău	17,0%	11,8%	5,3%	19,3%	13,8%	5,5%
Caraş Severin	9,5%	7,5%	2,0%	15,3%	5,3%	10,0%
Călăraşi	11,5%	11,3%	0,3%	26,3%	15,8%	10,5%
Cluj	2,9%	1,3%	1,5%	8,8%	3,3%	5,5%
Constanţa	11,8%	8,5%	3,3%	16,8%	16,5%	0,3%
Covasna	11,3%	7,0%	4,3%	10,0%	7,8%	2,3%
Dâmboviţa	9,3%	8,3%	1,0%	18,5%	13,5%	5,0%
Dolj	10,6%	10,9%	-0,2%	23,8%	17,3%	6,4%
Galaţi	13,0%	11,3%	1,8%	18,3%	14,8%	3,5%
Giurgiu	15,8%	9,0%	6,8%	23,0%	11,5%	11,5%
Gorj	11,8%	7,8%	4,0%	16,8%	12,0%	4,8%
Harghita	11,5%	8,5%	3,0%	16,5%	13,5%	3,0%
Hunedoara	5,5%	5,0%	0,5%	12,3%	6,5%	5,8%
Ialomiţa	12,5%	7,5%	5,0%	20,8%	12,3%	8,5%
Iaşi	9,0%	6,8%	2,3%	17,5%	12,8%	4,8%
Ilfov	5,3%	4,5%	0,8%	5,0%	3,3%	1,8%
Maramureş	9,5%	9,3%	0,3%	17,0%	10,5%	6,5%
Mehedinţi	14,3%	11,3%	3,0%	19,0%	13,3%	5,8%
Mureş	11,8%	15,3%	-3,5%	18,3%	11,8%	6,5%
Neamţ	8,3%	7,5%	0,8%	17,3%	12,0%	5,3%
Olt	8,8%	4,0%	4,8%	23,3%	13,8%	9,5%
Prahova	8,0%	5,3%	2,8%	13,8%	7,5%	6,3%
Satu Mare	10,5%	9,0%	1,5%	24,0%	15,5%	8,5%
Sălaj	10,0%	6,8%	3,3%	12,0%	9,5%	2,5%
Sibiu	9,8%	6,5%	3,3%	12,5%	11,0%	1,5%
Suceava	7,8%	8,3%	-0,5%	17,3%	13,3%	4,0%
Teleorman	12,8%	9,3%	3,5%	23,5%	13,8%	9,8%
Timiş	5,5%	3,5%	2,0%	11,8%	6,3%	5,5%
Tulcea	11,5%	8,3%	3,3%	16,0%	9,0%	7,0%
Vaslui	10,0%	7,8%	2,3%	23,5%	16,5%	7,0%
Vâlcea	9,8%	10,0%	-0,3%	14,3%	8,5%	5,8%
Vrancea	13,8%	12,8%	1,0%	22,5%	12,3%	10,3%
Romania	10,1%	7,8%	2,3%	16,7%	10,8%	5,9%

Source: authors' calculations.

Secondly, in terms of citizens' predisposition, data show that in Romania the economic constraints have an important role. There is a negative correlation between GDP per capita and the individuals' willingness to be involved in a clientelistic relationship with political parties or persons (Figure 4).

We expressed the values as the share of GDP per capita in median GDP per capita (average for 2010-2020 period) to highlight the disparities among Romanian counties and, usually, the share of respondents that are open to being involved in a clientelistic relationship with political parties or persons that approach them is higher in Vaslui, Teleorman, Botoșani, Giurgiu, Olt, or Mehedinți, counties with one of the lowest shares in national GDP per capita median.

Figure 4. Relationship between citizens' willingness and GDP per capita disparity

Source: authors' calculations

The impact of economic constraints on the individual's propensity to be engaged in clientelistic transactions is strengthened by the direct correlation with the capacity of the labor market to provide jobs. In counties with a higher unemployment rate (expressed as the share of unemployment in total employment at the county level) the citizens' willingness to be involved in clientelistic transactions is also at a high level, more than 10% of respondents (see Figure 5).

We choose to use the ratio between unemployed and employed persons to calculate the rate of unemployment and not to active persons (15-64 years or 20-64 years) to avoid some statistical glitches and to have a better look at the local labor market. The first reason is connected with the large share of the population employed in subsistence agriculture – especially in counties with a low level of industrialization and low GDP per capita (South and North-East counties). They are considered employed although they aren't involved in market activities.

The second reason is related to temporary/seasonal migration that can generate an underestimated unemployment rate in some counties. In Romania, during different periods of the year,

a large number of active persons are working abroad, especially in seasonal activities like agriculture, tourism, or construction. They aren't excluded from the active population and also can't be considered unemployed persons.

Figure 5. Relationship between citizens' willingness and the unemployment rate

Source: authors' calculations

Clientelism and public expenditures at the local level

Further, the incidence of clientelism perception was correlated with public spending of local authorities and the preference of the local politicians for passive expenditures (the share of personnel and social assistance spending) or investment expenditures (capital spending and European funds).

As Figure 6 shows, in 39 of the 42 counties in Romania, the local authorities directed a larger share of expenditures towards passive spending between 2010 and 2020, with the exception of Ilfov, Bistrița-Năsăud, and Giurgiu.

At the same time, Figure 7 shows that there is a negative correlation (the correlation remains negative if one considers București an outlier and excludes it from the analysis) between the share of passive expenditures in total expenditures at the county level, and the GDP per capita in the same period: the poorer counties are spending more than richer counties for public employment and social benefits.

Taking into account the correlation matrix (results available upon request from the authors) between the indicators for clientelism types (four types for positive clientelism and four types for negative clientelism), economic indicators (GDP per capita and unemployment rate), and local public expenditures (social benefits, personnel, passive expenditures, and investment spending), we can draw some conclusions regarding the relationship between clientelism and public expenditure at the county level in Romania.

First, **GDP per capita** is significantly negatively correlated with clientelism via social benefits offering and losing social benefits, both positive and negative overall clientelism, and also with the willingness of individuals to be involved in the clientelistic transaction. Also, the GDP per capita indicator is negatively correlated with social benefits spending of local public authorities and also with passive expenditures. Second, **the unemployment rate** is significantly positively correlated with social benefits offering and losing social benefits, positive clientelism and negative clientelism overall incidence and willingness of individuals. Also, here we can mention the correlation between the unemployment rate and personnel expenditures as the underdevelopment of the private sector leave the public sector to be the most important employer at the local level. Lastly, **passive expenditures (personnel and social assistance benefits)** are significantly positively correlated with social benefits clientelism incidence at the local level, but also with GDP per capita and unemployment rate.

Conclusions and further discussion

In Romania, the economic disparities are huge among counties and deeply embedded in the local structural conditions. This article correlates the economic disparities, clientelism incidence at the county level, and public expenditures in Romania and assesses how the local public expenditures (especially personnel and social protection) are a potential monetary vehicle between “patrons” and “clients”.

Based on our survey results, a first conclusion is that willingness of individuals and also the clientelistic approaches have usually a higher incidence at local elections than national (parliamentary) elections as the local political pressures to remain or to re-gain the power are higher. Moreover, in line with different other studies on the subject, we demonstrate that the greater the economic constraint is at the local level, the higher is the individuals’ willingness to be involved in a clientelistic relationship with political parties or persons.

A second conclusion is that the positive clientelistic approaches described in the Methodology section have a great incidence at the local level rather than negative types of clientelism. Even though the current paper shows only the correlation between clientelism incidence and two types of public spending (personnel and social) and not a clear causality relationship, we contribute to the debate regarding the demand-driven clientelism in Romania and how economic constraints (low GDP per capita, high unemployment rate) of the citizens determine a higher willingness of individuals to accept clientelistic approaches from the politicians at the local level. At the same time, the incidence of clientelism is usually higher in counties where the individual's demand is high and available to different types of clientelistic approaches (money, jobs in the public sector, social benefits, and access to public goods and services).

As a further discussion, this could be an important next step in debating the clientelistic linkages in post-communist Romania to see if there are parties that are specialized in a specific type of approach (negative or positive) and how this interaction developed during the last 30 years. Also, another interesting point could be how political clientelistic strategies influenced the long-term welfare of individuals at the local level and if citizens' willingness to be involved in clientelistic transactions decreased or increased during the time.

Acknowledgements

The paper was funded by the Romanian Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding (UEFISCDI) for the period 2020-2022, project number: PN-III-P1-1.1-TE-2019-0460.

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